

Research Article

Moxibustion to Support Lactation in Dairy Cows: A Preliminary Pilot Study.

Karla Pinto^{1,2,*}, Maria Begoña Criado³ .

¹ Department of Veterinary Sciences, University of Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD), Vila Real, Portugal;

² Animal and Veterinary Research Centre (CECAV) – Associate Laboratory for Animal and Veterinary Science (AL4Animals), UTAD, Vila Real, Portugal;

³ 1H-TOXRUN - One Health Toxicology Research Unit, University Institute of Health Sciences (IUCS), CESPU, Gandra, Portugal;

⁴ ICBAS – School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal.

* Correspondence: karlapintovet@gmail.com; jmachado@icbas.up.pt

Abstract

The objective of this preliminary study was to evaluate the potential role of moxibustion as a supportive intervention in lactating dairy cows, with particular attention to physiological balance and animal well-being. Ten Holstein-Frisian cows in lactation were randomly allocated into two groups of five animals each. Cows in Group I received moxibustion applied to predefined dorsal points corresponding to the Bladder Channel and Governor Vessel. Treatment sessions lasted between five and ten minutes, with four interventions performed over a two-week period (two sessions per week). Group II (control) was not subjected to therapeutic intervention and daily milk production was recorded under routine farm conditions.

During the intervention period, cows receiving moxibustion demonstrated an increase in mean daily milk production compared to their baseline week. A statistically significant increase ($p < 0.05$) was observed in one animal during intervention days. Although the small sample size and short monitoring period limit definitive conclusions, the findings suggest that moxibustion may represent a feasible complementary approach deserving further investigation under controlled experimental conditions.

Keywords: Moxibustion; Dairy cows; Traditional Chinese Veterinary Medicine; Animal Well-being.

Citation: Pinto K. Criado M.B., Machado J. Moxibustion to Support Lactation in Dairy Cows: A Preliminary Pilot Study. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2026;4(3)
doi: [10.5281/zenodo.20158070](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20158070)

Academic Editor: Jorge Rodrigues

Received: 3 March 2026
Reviewed: 25 March 2026
Revised: 10 May 2026
Accepted: 12 May 2026
Published: 13 May 2026

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2026 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Modern dairy production increasingly recognises that animal welfare is intrinsically linked to physiological stability and productive balance. Milk yield is not only a function of genetics and nutrition but is also influenced by stress, environmental conditions, and the quality of human–animal interactions. Physiological stress responses can alter endocrine function and potentially interfere with lactation mechanisms ^{1,2}.

Interest in complementary veterinary approaches has expanded in recent decades, particularly where such techniques may contribute to improved comfort, reduced stress reactivity, and enhanced physiological regulation without reliance on pharmacological interventions ³.

According to Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), lactation is understood as the transformation of *Xue* (blood) into milk, a process primarily associated with the functional activity of the Centre (Stomach and Spleen). Milk production depends on the adequate movement of *Qi* and *Xue*, as well as the harmonious interaction of the Heart and Kidney ^{4,5}.

Within the Heidelberg model of TCM, physiological balance is interpreted as a regulated vegetative functional state. Therapeutic interventions such as acupuncture and moxibustion aim to restore functional coherence and promote systemic regulation ^{5,6}.

Moxibustion consists of the application of thermal stimulation through the combustion of dried leaves of *Artemisia vulgaris* near or on specific acupuncture points⁷⁻⁹. The gradual and uniform heat produced may be able to stimulate local and systemic regulatory mechanisms^{7,9,10}.

In veterinary practice, moxibustion has been applied in cattle for several conditions¹¹⁻¹⁵. According to Kothbauer *et al.*¹⁶, acupuncture and moxibustion may positively influence functional disorders in cattle, especially when integrated with conventional veterinary diagnostics.

From a physiological standpoint, thermal stimulation up to approximately 45°C may activate autonomic afferent pathways, particularly C fibers, potentially influencing local circulation and neurovegetative balance¹⁷. Some reports suggest that neuroendocrine modulation, including possible oxytocin involvement, may occur following acupuncture-related interventions¹⁸.

In this context, the present pilot study aimed to explore whether moxibustion applied to selected dorsal points could support lactation stability in dairy cows.

Materials and Methods

Animals and Study Design

Ten Holstein-Frisian lactating cows were included and randomly allocated into two groups:

- Group I (intervention) - five cows treated with moxibustion over two weeks in a total of 4 sessions.
- Group II (control) - five cows monitored without therapeutic intervention during the same period.

One week prior to the intervention phase, daily milk production was recorded in all animals to establish baseline production levels.

Application Procedure

The moxibustion procedure involved four steps: preparation of 5 cm diameter moxa balls; gentle restraint of the cow in a containment trunk; application of miso paste to secure the moxa; and ignition of the moxa balls. Each application lasted between five and ten minutes and was discontinued if any signs of discomfort were observed.

Figure 1 and 2 represent the application procedure.

Figure 1. Cow with ignited moxa balls.

Figure 2. Close-up of the moxa balls' location and application.

Acupuncture Points

The selected dorsal points included GV 6, GV 5, GV 4-1, GV 4, GV 20-B, Bladder 28-1, GV 2, an extra point over GV 6, and Bladder 21. These points are traditionally associated with strengthening *Qi* and *Xue*, harmonising digestive function, and supporting systemic regulation¹⁹, and are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Visual representation of the location of the acupoints employed in this study.

Statistical Analysis

Daily milk production (litres) was compiled using Excel XP and analysed with SPSS 17 for Windows®. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Comparisons were performed between baseline and intervention periods and between intervention and control groups.

Ethical Approval

All experimental procedures performed in this study were reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences of the University of Porto, Portugal (Protocol Approval Number: n°006/2012). The research protocol adhered to the principles of the 3Rs (Replacement, Reduction, and Refinement). The number of cattle used was minimised. As well, every effort was made to minimise pain, distress, and discomfort throughout the acupuncture interventions. Animals were monitored daily for signs of stress, and veterinary care was available at all times. This study involved client-owned animals. Written informed consent was obtained from the animal owners prior to the commencement of the study. Owners were fully informed of the procedures, potential risks, and benefits, and retained the right to withdraw their animals from the study at any time without prejudice to their ongoing veterinary care.

Results

At baseline, mean daily milk production in Group I was 36.42 litres, increasing to 38.56 litres during the intervention period. In Group II, baseline production was 30.28 litres, increasing to 31.45 litres over the same period. An increase in milk production was observed in the intervention group during treatment weeks compared to baseline. A statistically significant increase ($p = 0.034$) was detected in one cow (638) during intervention days. Group-level increases were moderate but consistent, whereas production in the control group showed smaller and more irregular fluctuations. Two animals were excluded during the study due to unrelated health events (fracture and pneumonia). Table 1 shows the production data retrieved for this experiment.

Table 1: Production of dairy cows in the test group (cows 638, 667, 680 and 704) and control group (cows 617, 670, 727 and 730). Note: the day 1 to 7 was the period of milk production of the two groups before the experimental phase serving only as a control period (average daily milk production before the intervention).

Quantity (in litres) of milk produced										
Day	617	638	667	670	680	704	727	730	725 ¹⁾	668 ²⁾
1	43	37	32	21	37	38,5	36	27	38	52
2	44	39	35	21	40	39	36	27	37	51
3	40	36	33	21	39,5	41,5	35	29,5	38	53
4	37	36,5	34,5	22	38	40,5	35	26,5	37,5	49
5	37	34	35	20,5	34	37	34,5	24	37	48
6	38	36,5	31	19,5	38	36,5	33	25,5	35	48
7	35	37,5	27	22,5	37	39,5	31	26,5	37,5	52
Beginning of intervention										
8	37	37,5	31	21	38	38	35,5	27,5	38	46
9 ³⁾	40	39,5	31	19	41	39	33,5	26	39	49
10	41	36	35	23	39	39	33,5	26	-	50
11	42	37	35	22,5	42	40	36	28	-	51
12 ³⁾	42	39	37	23	42	40	35	29,5	-	53
13	36	37	33,5	22	39	40	37	27,5	-	49
14	39	37	33,5	22	39	40	37	28	-	50
Start of week two										
15	39	38	36	23,5	42	40	37	28	-	-
16 ³⁾	41	41	38	22	44	41	35,5	28	-	-
17	42	38	37	24	44	42	38	29	-	-
18	41	38	36,5	24	41	41	35,5	29	-	-
19 ³⁾	43	39	37	25	42,5	41	36	28	-	-
20	39	38	36	22	39	40	35	26	-	-
21	37	38	37	22	42	40	35	27,5	-	-

1) Animal excluded from the study due to death (complete fracture of the humerus, was euthanised).

2) Animal excluded from the study due to illness (pneumonia).

3) Dates of the sessions of moxibustion.

Discussion

This pilot study explored the feasibility and potential physiological impact of moxibustion in lactating dairy cows. The observed increases in milk production during intervention days may suggest a short-term modulatory effect.

From a TCM perspective, thermal stimulation may promote *Qi* and *Xue* movement and enhance functional regulation^{20,21}. From a physiological standpoint, localised heat may influence autonomic tone and circulation²². The possible involvement of oxytocin and prolactin production has been suggested in acupuncture literature¹⁸, although this was not measured in the present study. Stress is known to influence physiological processes and lactation¹, and dairy cattle welfare is strongly influenced by handling quality and human–animal interactions². Although restraint procedures were necessary for the intervention, no reduction in milk production was observed on treatment days, which may suggest that the thermal stimulation and its procedures did not negatively impact physiological balance.

Environmental temperature is another relevant factor in dairy production. Holstein-Frisian cows have a thermal neutral zone between 5°C and 21°C²³. Despite elevated ambient temperatures during the first intervention session (approximately 30°C); milk production did not decline in treated animals.

The principal limitations of this study include the small sample size, short duration, lack of sham treatment, and absence of hormonal or behavioural measurements. Therefore, conclusions must remain cautious.

Future studies should include larger sample sizes (minimum 30 animals per group), sham-controlled designs, standardised handling procedures, extended monitoring periods, behavioural welfare indicators, and endocrine measurements to clarify potential mechanisms.

Conclusion

This preliminary pilot study suggests that moxibustion is feasible in dairy cattle and may support lactation stability without observable negative effects during the intervention period. While the results cannot establish efficacy, they encourage further controlled investigations into complementary veterinary approaches aimed at supporting physiological balance and animal well-being.

Credit author statement: Conceptualisation: K.P.; Investigation: K.P.; Writing, reviewing and editing: K.P.; M.B.C. and J.P.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: No financial support was received.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Institutional Review Board Statement: All experimental procedures performed in this study were reviewed and approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences of the University of Porto, Portugal (Protocol Approval Number: n°006/2012).

Informed Consent Statement: Written informed consent was obtained from the animal owners prior to the commencement of the study.

Data Availability Statement: The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

References

1. Breazile JE. The physiology of stress and its relationship to mechanisms of disease and therapeutics. *Vet Clin North Am Food Anim Pract.* 1988;4(3):441-80. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0749-0720\(15\)31025-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0749-0720(15)31025-2)
2. Peters M, Silveira I, Machado Filho L, Machado A, Pereira L. Aversive management in dairy cattle and effects on well-being, behaviour and productive aspects. 2010.
3. Schoen AM. *Veterinary Acupuncture: Ancient Art to Modern Medicine*: Mosby; 2001. 9780323009454.
4. Campiglia H. Domínio do Yin: Da Fertilidade à Maternidade; A Mulher e suas Fases Segundo a Medicina Tradicional Chinesa: Ícone editora; 2022. 9788527412988.
5. Greten HJ. Understanding TCM: Scientific Chinese medicine – The Heidelberg model. Preliminary, unrevised course version ed2008.

6. Greten HJ. Chinese medicine as vegetative systems biology. Part I: therapeutic methods. HNO. 2011;59(12):1160-4. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00106-011-2409-6>
7. Chiu J-H. How does moxibustion possibly work? Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine. 2013;2013(1):198584.
8. Dawes NC, Anastasi JK. The Case for Moxibustion for Painful Syndromes: History, principles and rationale. Current research in complementary & alternative medicine. 2022;6(1). doi: <https://doi.org/10.29011/2577-2201.100053>
9. Deng H, Shen X. The mechanism of moxibustion: ancient theory and modern research. Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine. 2013;2013(1):379291.
10. Hu D, Shen W, Gong C, Fang C, Yao C, Zhu X, et al. Grain-sized moxibustion promotes NK cell antitumour immunity by inhibiting adrenergic signalling in non-small cell lung cancer. Journal of cellular and molecular medicine. 2021;25(6):2900-8.
11. Jang KH, Lee JM, Nam TC. Electroacupuncture and moxibustion for correction of abomasal displacement in dairy cattle. J Vet Sci. 2003;4(1):93-5.
12. Korematsu K, Takagi E, Kawabe T, Nakao T, Moriyoshi M, Kawata K. Therapeutic effects of moxibustion on delayed uterine involution in postpartum dairy cows. J Vet Med Sci. 1993;55(4):613-6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1292/jvms.55.613>
13. Lee JY, Lee MR, Kim JH, Han TS, Kang SS, Bae CS, et al. Efficacy of moxibustion after rolling correction in dairy cows with abomasal displacement. Am J Chin Med. 2007;35(1):63-7. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1142/s0192415x0700462x>
14. Zhong YM, Cheng B, Zhang LL, Lu WT, Shang YN, Zhou HY. Effect of Moxibustion on Inflammatory Cytokines in Animals with Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine : eCAM. 2020;2020:6108619. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/6108619>
15. Holyoak GR, Ma A. Evidence-Based Application of Acupuncture in Theriogenology. Veterinary Sciences [Internet]. 2022; 9(2):[53 p.]. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/vetsci9020053>
16. Kothbauer O, van Engelenburg G. Acupuncture in Cattle. In: Schoen AM, editor. Veterinary Acupuncture: Ancient Art to Modern Medicine. 2nd ed. St. Louis: Mosby; 2001. p. 449-70. 978-0323004497.
17. Draehmpaehl D, Zohmann A. Acupuncture in the Dog and Cat: Scientific Principles and Practice. Ames: Iowa State University Press; 1994. 59-61 p. 978-0813813943.
18. Jenner C, Filshie J. Galactorrhoea following acupuncture. Acupuncture in medicine : journal of the British Medical Acupuncture Society. 2002;20(2-3):107-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1136/aim.20.2-3.107>
19. Porkert M, Hempten CH. Classical Acupuncture: The Standard Textbook: Phainon Ed. and Media, Acta Medicinæ Sinensis; 1995. 9783895200083.
20. Yamamura Y. Acupuntura tradicional: a arte de inserir: Roca; 1993. 9788572410786.
21. Xie H, Preast V. Xie's Veterinary Acupuncture: Wiley; 2013. 9781118692196.
22. Draehmpaehl D, Zohmann A. Acupuntura no cão e no gato: princípios básicos e prática científica: Roca; 1997. 9788572412261.
23. Neiva RS. Produção de bovinos leiteiros. 2. ed. Lavras: UFLA; 2000.